

MUSIC FOR THE GRAMMAR SKILLS ENHANCEMENT: DECRYPTION OF TRIBAL STUDENTS PERCEPTION

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Paper Received On: 20 NOV 2024

Peer Reviewed On: 24 DEC 2024

Published On: 01 JAN 2025

Abstract

The paper is an outcome of an experimental study aimed to determine the effectiveness of the 'Music-Based Program' used in teaching English grammar to tribal students. The effectiveness was statistically measured with the perception of the tribal students towards the Music-Based Program using the intensity index and percentage analysis. The overall intensity index of 4.76 on the reaction scale demonstrated that the tribal students' perceptions were favorable towards the music-based program for enhancing English grammar skills through music. It is in line with the NEP-2020, which underlines cultural art-integrated learning.

Keywords: *Music -Based Program, Grammar skills Enhancement, Tribal Students.*

1.0 INTRODUCTION:

Today, people are observed enjoying karaoke displays no matter where they go. They can simultaneously hear the music and read the lyrics; language and music have a perceived connection. Researchers have claimed a significant link between humans, music, and means of expression and language (Pinker,2002 & Silva,2006). Storr (1992) rightly says, "Since our forefathers painted cave paintings depicting people dancing in the caverns, music has dwelled in human life since ancient times, and it is proven." Furthermore, the human foetus also comprehends acoustic signals while developing in the womb, after birth, and the first aspect of

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language that babies acquire is music, which includes intonation, pitch, and rhythm (Mora, 2000). Lecanuet et al., mentioned by Murphey (1990:98), discovered that while still in the mother's womb, the foetus can detect melodies and mother's intonation. Campbell's (2001) study is proof of music's importance in the development of a foetus. Musical intelligence is the first to be overtly demonstrated in children (Gardner, 2011). According to 'The Mozart Effect,' initially described in 1993 by Rauscher et al., music improves learning in all areas, including spatial-temporal intelligence, mathematical talents, and abstract reasoning are the few examples of it (Cacciafesta et al., 2010). According to the new National Education Policy-2020 (NEP-2020), tribal art and music have to be integrated as innovative pedagogical techniques for such tribal-specific learners. Hence, music and its pedagogical importance need to be reviewed.

1.1 MUSIC: MEANING AND CONCEPT

Music is a generic and universal term that is used differently through time immemorial. According to Pt. Vishnu Narayan Bhatkhande (1909), "Indian musicology records, Sharangdev, of 13th century, in his book of musicology 'Sangeet-Ratnakar' defines music in Sanskrit as "Geetam, Vadyam Tathaa Nrutyam, Tryayam Sangeet Muchyayante" which means "Music is the blend of all the three: Singing, Percussion, and Dance". As is commonly believed, a song is a text written to be sung (Dave, 2013), therefore, the importance of music in the teaching of English is emphasized.

1.2 IMPORTANCE OF MUSIC FOR TRIBALS

Music is the essence of indigenous, ethnic people's culture. The cultural traditions of the country's diverse tribal regions reflect the fantastic range of India's regional tribal folk music. Each region has its own distinct aesthetic of music culture. (Vidyarthi & Rai, 1985) Tribal, indigenous folk music is not taught in a structured manner; it is the soul of their living. Music and songs are daily activities that allow them to express their feelings about every moment and incident of their lives. Music is imbibed from childhood in the Tribal hamlets and heard and ingested with various public performances. Tribals can practice and hone their talents through these activities, festivals, and performances. Music is a must-have component of every moment in the tribal culture, weddings, engagements, and births; several songs are suitable for such times and celebrations. As music and songs are an integral part of the tribal culture, music will undoubtedly apply to these indigenous students in their formal education. The whole tone of the instructional process will be changed from one that is threatening to one that is enjoyable, and this change of tone will maximize receptiveness in the students (Murphey, 1992). English

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grammar skill enhancement is one of the must-have components of English language teaching and learning; hence, music as a pedagogical tool could make the English grammar teaching and learning process more enjoyable, engaging, and sustainable for tribal students. Therefore, the researcher decided to develop and intervene in the Music Based Program (MBP) for tribal students to enhance their grammar skills. It aimed to measure the reaction of the students towards the Music-Based Program intervened in the teaching of English Grammar through music.

1.3. METHOD & MATERIAL:

The proposed study was experimental, wherein a quasi-experimental design was used. The pre-test, post-test, and non-equivalent control group design was followed. The study was delimited to English Grammar of class IX students of Marathi Medium Tribal Ashram Schools affiliated to Maharashtra State Board of Secondary and Higher Secondary Education (MSBSHSE). The sample for the study was selected using a convenient sampling technique. The material used for the study were;

i) MUSIC-BASED PROGRAM

The Music-based Program for grammar teaching consisted of A set of 10 grammar songs and English song-based activities with accompanying instrumental karaoke music. The grammar songs prepared by the researcher were based on the class IX syllabus grammar topics' content, and various song-based activities were designed in the lesson plans under it. A total of 64 lesson sessions were planned according to the topic and the subtopics.

ii) REACTION SCALE:

The researcher constructed a Likert-type five-point reaction scale to get the students' reaction toward the music-based Program used for teaching English grammar. The scale was comprised of 25 statements. The reaction scale was used to measure the usability, practicality, and effectiveness in terms of enhancing English grammar skills through a music-based program. The scale was administered to the experimental group of students only.

1.4 PLAN & PROCEDURE

The study was conducted in four phases.

Phase 1. Development of Music-Based Program for Grammar Teaching: The researcher developed the Music-Based Program based on the grammar content analysis of the English textbook of class IX. The verses comprising the grammar rules and their usage were prepared as a central component of the Music-Based Program for English grammar teaching.

Phase 2. Pre-Test Phase: English Grammar Achievement written and oral test was prepared and administered to the control and experimental groups to make the groups equivalent.

Phase 3. Implementation Phase of the Music-Based Program: The researcher implemented grammar teaching to the experimental group of students through a music-based program for one academic year. The control group was conventionally taught English Grammar. Based on class IX's prescribed grammar topics, the researcher prepared 64 lesson plans to teach grammar through a Music-Based Program. Grammar songs-based and English songs-based activities were integrated into the lesson plans.

Phase 4. Post-Test: A 100-mark English Grammar Skills Achievement Test consisting of an English Oral Grammar skill Achievement Test of 50 marks and an English Written Grammar skills Test of 50 marks was administered to the experimental and control groups as the post-test. The reaction scale was administered to the experimental group to measure their reactions toward the teaching of English Grammar through the Music-Based Program.

1.5. DATA ANALYSIS

The collected data was analyzed quantitatively using Percentage analysis and Intensity Index. The following table and graph are represented below for the analysis details.

Table No. 1 The Reaction Scale Analysis using Percentage and Intensity Index

Strongly Agree: SA, Agree: A, Undecided: UD, Disagree: DA, Strongly Disagree: SD

No.	Statements	%	%	%	%	%	INTENSITY INDEX
		SA	A	UD	D	SD	
		98%	2%	0%	0%	0%	
1	All the grammar topics in the syllabus were covered while teaching through music.	45	1	0	0	0	4.98
		83%	17%	0%	0%	0%	
2	Teaching through music enhanced the understanding of grammar topics.	38	8	0	0	0	4.83
		70%	17%	13%	0%	0%	
3	Teaching through music effectively met the grammar learning objectives.	32	8	6	0	0	4.57
		83%	17%	0%	0%	0%	
4	The grammar songs used were very useful for learning grammar topics easily.	38	8	0	0	0	4.83
		87%	13%	0%	0%	0%	
5	Learning grammar through music is a new way to learn grammar.	40	6	0	0	0	4.87
		85%	15%	0%	0%	0%	

6	Singing the grammar songs and activity songs during classes were joyful.	39	7	0	0	0	4.85
		93%	7%	0%	0%	0%	
7	All the tunes of grammar songs were easy to sing melodiously.	43	3	0	0	0	4.93
		98%	2%	0%	0%	0%	
8	Tribal music, known to us, was used in the teaching of grammar.	45	1	0	0	0	4.98
		80%	20%	0%	0%	0%	
9	Grammar songs were easy to remember due to their familiar tune.	37	9	0	0	0	4.80
		80%	20%	0%	0%	0%	
10	The songs came to my mind automatically, even after the classes.	37	9	0	0	0	4.80
		80%	20%	0%	0%	0%	
11	This was by far the most enjoyable experience in grammar learning.	37	9	0	0	0	4.80
		74%	15%	11%	0%	0%	
12	All the grammar topics taught were completed in the given time period.	34	7	5	0	0	4.63
		70%	13%	17%	0%	0%	
13	Adequate time was given to perform and present during the song-based activities.	32	6	8	0	0	4.52
		0%	0%	0%	22%	78%	
							4.78
14	Music did not create a joyful atmosphere while learning grammar.	0	0	0	10	36	
15	The song-based activities were very engaging during grammar learning.	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%	
		37	9	0	0	0	4.80
16	The lyrics of the songs could be understood.	78%	9%	13%	0%	0%	
		36	4	6	0	0	4.65
		78%	17%	4%	0%	0%	
17	The songs used in the activities were appropriate to suit the grammar topics.	36	8	2	0	0	4.74
		%	0%	2%	22%	76%	
18	The song-based activities were not interesting for me to learn grammar.	00	0	1	10	35	4.74
		0%	0%	0%	30%	70%	
19	The song-based activities did not motivate grammar learning.	0	0	0	14	32	4.70

		0%	0%	0%	20%	80%	
20	The music used in the lessons was distracting.	0	0	0	9	37	4.80
		0%	0%	9%	20%	72%	
21	There was no enhancement of grammar skills in my writing.	0	0	4	9	33	4.63
		0%	0%	26%	28%	46%	
22	There was no enhancement of grammar skills in my speaking.	0	0	12	13	21	4.20
		96%	4%	0%	0%	0%	
23	The overall teaching of grammar through music was liked.	44	2	0	0	0	4.96
		98%	2%	0%	0%	0%	
24	Grammar learning through music in the future should be continued.	45	1	0	0	0	4.98
		87%	13%	0%	0%	0%	
25	Music should be included in grammar teaching.	40	6	0	0	0	4.87
Average Intensity Index							4.76

Table No.2: Graphical Representation of the Reaction Scale Analysis: Percentage

Table No.3: Graphical Representation of Intensity Index of the Reaction Scale**INTERPRETATIONS: RESULTS**

1. 98% of the students strongly agreed, and 2% agreed with the statement that all the grammar topics in the syllabus were covered while teaching through music. The intensity index was 4.98 and shows favorable reactions.
2. 83% of the students strongly agreed, and 17% of students agreed that teaching through music enhanced their understanding of grammar topics. The intensity index was 4.83.
3. 70% of the students strongly agreed, 17% agreed, and 13% marked undecided on the statement that teaching through music effectively met the grammar learning objectives. The intensity index was 4.57.
4. 83% of the students strongly agreed, and 17% of students agreed with the statement that the grammar songs used were very useful for learning grammar topics easily. The intensity index was 4.83.
5. 87% of the students strongly agreed, and 13% agreed that learning grammar through music is a new way to learn grammar. The intensity index was 4.87.
6. 85% of the students strongly agreed, and 15% of students agreed with the statement that they enjoyed singing grammar songs and activity songs during classes. The intensity index was 4.85.
7. 93% of the students strongly agreed, and 7% of students agreed with the statement that all the tunes of grammar songs were easy to sing melodiously. The intensity index was 4.93.

8. 98% of the students strongly agreed, and 2% of students agreed with the statement that the tribal music, known to us, was used in the teaching of grammar. The intensity index was 4.98.
9. 80% of the students strongly agreed, and 20% of students agreed with the statement that grammar songs were easy to remember due to their familiar tune. The intensity index was 4.80.
10. 80% of the students strongly agreed, and 20% agreed that the songs came into their minds automatically, even after the classes. The intensity index was 4.80.
11. 80% of the students strongly agreed, and 20% agreed that it was by far the most enjoyable experience in grammar learning. The intensity index was 4.80.
12. 74% of the students strongly agreed, 15% agreed, and 11% marked undecided on the statement that all the grammar topics were taught and completed in the given time period. The intensity index was 4.63.
13. 70% of the students strongly agreed, 13% agreed, and 17% were undecided on the statement that adequate time was given to the song-based activities. The intensity index was 4.52.
14. 78% of the students strongly disagreed, and 22% of students disagreed with the 14th statement. The intensity index of 4.78 demonstrated that their reaction favored that the Music created a Joyful atmosphere while learning grammar.
15. 80% of the students strongly agreed, and 20% of students agreed with the statement that the song-based activities were very engaging during grammar learning. The intensity index was 4.80.
16. 78% of the students strongly agreed, 9% agreed, and 13% marked undecided about whether they could understand the lyrics of the songs. The intensity index was 4.65.
17. 78% of the students strongly agreed, 17% agreed, and 4% marked undecided on the statement that the songs used in the activities were appropriate for the grammar topics. The intensity index of 4.74.
18. 76% of the students strongly disagreed, 22% disagreed, and 2% could not agree with the statement, no. 18. The intensity index of 4.74 demonstrated that their reaction favored the enjoyable song-based activities for me to learn grammar.

19 70% of the students strongly disagreed, and 30% disagreed with the 19th statement, The intensity index of 4.70 demonstrated that their reaction favored the song-based activities that motivated grammar learning.

20 80% of the students strongly disagreed, and 20% disagreed with the statement no. 20 The intensity index of 4.80 demonstrated that their reaction was in favor that they did not feel distracted from learning due to the music used in the lessons.

21 72% of the students strongly disagreed, 20% disagreed, and 9% marked undecided for 21st statement. The intensity index of 4.63 demonstrated favourable reactions towards enhancing of their grammar skills.

22 46% of the students strongly disagreed, 28% disagreed, and 26% marked undecided on the 22nd statement. The intensity index of 4.20 demonstrated favourable reactions that S/he, found enhancement of grammar skills in speaking skills.

23 96% of the students strongly agreed, and 4% agreed with the statement, “I liked the overall teaching of grammar through music.” The intensity index was 4.96

24 98% of the students strongly agreed, and 2% of students agreed with the statement, “I would like to continue grammar learning through music in the future also.” The intensity index was 4.98.

25 87% of the students strongly agreed, and 13% agreed that music should be included in grammar teaching. The intensity index of 4.87 demonstrated that their reaction was favorable.

DISCUSSION:

The findings of the study revealed that the average intensity index score of the reaction scale was 4.76. It demonstrated a favorable perception of the students toward the Music-Based Program intervened for English grammar teaching. Therefore, it can be said that the students agreed with all positive statements about the Music-Based Program. Students' perceptions were unfavorable towards all the negative statements about the program in the reaction scale, which was prepared to measure the effectiveness of the Music-Based Program for enhancing English grammar skills. The overall intensity index of 4.76 was found with the average intensity index of the reaction scale, demonstrating that the tribal students' reactions were favorable towards the music-based program for enhancing English grammar skills through music. The findings are in line with the findings of Sebastian (2014), who found that the experience of learning with enjoyment and engagement benefitted the retention of learning. This is also consistent with the study by Bhamare (2017), who found that learners enjoy learning and are motivated when exposed to a non-academic environment where authentic materials like songs, films, and

videos support language learning. The use of Music-Based Programs to teach grammar to tribal learners, is in accordance with NEP -2020, highlights art-integrated learning. According to the new education policy, tribal art and music must be integrated as pedagogical techniques for tribal-specific learners. The successful results of such programs will open the door for policymakers, higher authorities, and educators in schools to make cognizant, purposeful, and systematic efforts to enhance the English grammar skills of students through a Music-Based Program. Hence, the findings have highly valued implications. School teachers can utilize the techniques for teaching English grammar content at the various levels of school education stages. An innovative pedagogical technique of teaching through music guided in the curriculum has implications for policymakers responsible for developing teacher education curricula at all levels. Principals and educational administrators can design training programs for schoolteachers and stakeholders to implement the technique for teaching English grammar. An innovative pedagogical teaching technique, through music, can be used other than teaching grammar in the English Language.

CONCLUSION

The study examined the effectiveness of the Music-Based Program in teaching English grammar through music to secondary-level tribal students. The overall intensity index of 4.76 on the reaction scale demonstrated that the tribal students' perceptions were favorable towards the music-based program for enhancing English grammar skills through music. This program proved effective in the student's enhancement of grammar skills in terms of achievement of written and oral grammar skills. Additionally, students' perceptions regarding the pedagogical technique of teaching grammar through music were favorable. The students also revealed that they never had such an entertaining and engaging experience of English grammar learning earlier. The researcher poetically draws study inferences as follows;

“Music provided enjoyment in the grammar learning process;
Enjoyment intertwined with engagement in the grammar learning process;
Engagement stimulated motivation for the grammar learning process;
Motivation facilitated the grammar skills enhancement process.”

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